

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Annotation: It is obvious that in today's fast-paced world knowing foreign languages plays a vital role in achieving personal and career success. According to statistics, more and more people are learning English language as it is becoming the language of the trade and technology. However, a lot of students are not willing to learn it as they easily frustrate during learning this language when they encounter with challenges and difficulties. This article delves into the importance of motivation in language learning and the ways of motivating and engaging English language learners.

Keywords: motivation, importance, clear goals, feedback, external and internal motivation

Introduction

Today English is one of the global languages and it has an important role in helping people to communicate and fit into the modern world. That's why day by day the number of its learners is increasing steadily and right now almost every country's educational system teaches English language as an independent subject. But according to results of surveys, many students are reluctant to learn this language as they easily feel discouragement when they start to learn English. So that reason considerable amount of researches are being carried out on students in order to find right and effective ways to motivate and engage them to learn English. In below we will try to seek the effective methods of pushing students to learn the language no matter how they find it difficult.

Main Part

Motivation is considered as one of the most important parts of achieving any goal in this life. The definition of motivation has been interpreted in different ways by

different scholars. Dornyei(2001) cited that motivation is a multifaceted concept that has been the subject of scholarly researches in different academic areas and no single available theory has yet captured its total complexity. While Gardner said that “motivation is a very complex phenomenon with many facets...thus it is not possible to give a simple definition”. From these opinions, we may understand the motivation as something that makes the person more energetic and pushes him towards his or her goals.

When it comes to language learning, we can find a lot of definitions of motivation. Gardner(1983), in his socio-educational model, considered that motivation is perceived to be composed of three elements such as :effort, desire and effect. The effort refers to the time the student spend on foreign language learning and the drive of the student. The desire indicates how much the student wants to become proficient in the language, while the effect means the student's emotional reactions which is related to language learning. In addition to this, Parson, Jonson and Brown(2001) defined motivation as an important component or factors in the learning process. Learning and motivation have the same importance in order to achieve something. Learning helps students gain knowledge and skills while motivation pushes them or encourages them to go through the learning process. Besides, Reeve (1996) suggests that : "Student's motivation is influenced by both internal and external factors that can start, sustain, intensify ,or discourage behaviour". From these states, we can conclude that motivation is what triggers the student to achieve something and it is necessary for everyone who is doing any important task.

In terms of the importance of motivation in foreign language learning process, the results of many previous researches show that motivation plays a significant role in the success or failure in a language learning. Spolsky(1990) cited that motivated students are likely to learn more quickly as opposed to the ones who are less motivated. In a specific learning situation, students who are less motivated are likely to lose their attention, to misbehave and to cause discipline problems. On the contrary, students who

are more highly motivated will participate actively and pay more attention to a certain learning task or activity.

Many scholars did researches about how to engage students and give them true triggers while teaching them a new language. One of these researchers is Jennifer Maguire wrote about how to motivate ESL students and gave 10 sure-fire ways to teachers to inspire language learners. They are :

- 1) Set clear goals with your students
- 2) Incorporate interactive and fun activities
- 3) Provide regular and constructive feedback
- 4) Create a supportive learning environment
- 5) Personalize the learning environment
- 6) Use technology to enhance learning
- 7) Encourage autonomous learning
- 8) Celebrate achievements
- 9) Connect lessons to real-life situations
- 10) Highlight the benefits of learning English

These are considered as practical and effective ways of motivating students to learn a language. But at the same time the teacher's motivation is as important as the student's. Because only the motivated and inspiring teacher can teach and push his or her students to do better.

In the past, there were a lot of researches related to motivation and language learning. One of them was carried out by Siriluck and Sirithip (2004) and it conducted a study about the relationship between motivation and proficiency in English language learning of undergraduate students. The results showed that the high English proficiency students are more motivated than low English proficiency students.

In addition, there are a lot of effective ways to motivate students and one of them is using authentic materials while teaching the language. We can count newspapers, magazines, TV shows, radio broadcasts or soap operas as the examples of authentic materials. They help to make the learning process more engaging and teach

students not only theory part of the language, but also the culture, lifestyle and different aspects of the life. Besides, teachers can use stories of the successful people and show them as a role-model to their students to achieve something not only in language learning but also in other fields of life. Also teaching style and the treatment of the teacher to his or her students may affect student's motivation to learn the language. That's why at first teachers should understand about the motivation's role and they learn about the ways of giving it for example treating students as an individual learner rather than comparing them to one another and so on.

Conclusion

In conclusion, motivation is a significant factor to learn the language successfully so that reason it is important to teachers to know the productive ways to energize their students by showing them right ways and giving them true motivation when they have lack of willingness to continue.

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